

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR DEVELOPING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN'S SPEECH THROUGH PLAY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18280363>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th January 2026

Accepted: 16th January 2026

Online: 17th January 2026

KEYWORDS

preschool education, speech
development, speech activity,
pedagogical approach,
communication

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the issues of speech development in preschool children from a pedagogical perspective. The features of phonetic, lexical, and grammatical speech formation, as well as ways to enhance children's speech activity, are examined. The study highlights the importance of the educational process content and pedagogical approaches in supporting speech development in preschool education.

Introduction

The preschool period is an important stage in a child's speech development. It is during this time that oral speech, vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammatical structures are formed. Speech is the main means by which a child communicates with the environment and directly influences intellectual, social, and emotional development. Therefore, the development of speech in preschool educational institutions is considered one of the most urgent pedagogical tasks.

For children, the most natural and interesting type of activity is play. During play, a child thinks freely, communicates, expresses emotions, and enriches speech experience. Therefore, the use of play technologies in speech development is highly effective.

1. The Importance of Play Activity in Speech Development

Play increases children's speech activity, expands vocabulary, and forms correct pronunciation. Through role-playing, didactic, and movement games, children enter into verbal communication, learn to ask and answer questions, and get used to expressing independent opinions. Play is a means of a child's intellectual development. During play, various mental processes become active, and the tasks and conditions of the game require concentration of attention, differentiation, comparison, and generalization.

Frequent repetition of similar actions and words creates stable connections in the child's mind about objects and events and helps form specific thoughts and behaviors.

Play is of great importance in the comprehensive development of children. During play, perception, thinking, imagination, memory, attention, will, emotions, and other psychological processes are involved. Games serve to develop children's mental activity and increase their intellectual initiative. They help shape children's feelings and activate sensory organs such as sight, touch, and hearing.

Didactic games are organized on the basis of various materials such as dolls, toys, colorful pictures and cards, different geometric shapes, and natural materials. In activities

with preschool children, the importance of didactic games is great. Their wide use positively influences the development of thinking, perception, intelligence, memory, will, and interest in learning. Children's curiosity about the surrounding world increases, and their alertness, voluntary attention, ingenuity, and initiative are strengthened.

Through play and through observing adults' actions, children form attitudes toward reality and are educated intellectually, morally, and physically.

Play determines how a child's future learning, work activity, and relationships with people will develop. Since ancient times, play has attracted the attention of pedagogues, psychologists, philosophers, ethnographers, and art scholars. Play is real life for children. Broad and multifaceted use of play means influencing the child in a comprehensive way through play.

Play should correspond to children's age characteristics. In the works of J. A. Comenius and E. A. Polkov, great attention is paid to children's play. Comenius stated: "Respect children's play; in raising true hardworking people, it is your best partner."

2. Pedagogical Conditions for Speech Development

To develop preschool children's speech through play, the following pedagogical conditions are important:

- creating a speech-developing play environment;
- taking age and individual characteristics into account;
- the teacher serving as a speech model;
- systematic and purposeful use of play technologies;
- encouraging children to communicate freely.

3. The Role of the Teacher

The teacher acts as a manager and guide of children's speech activity during play. The teacher teaches correct pronunciation, introduces new words into active speech, and corrects speech errors using gentle pedagogical methods. In preschool education, the teacher is the main subject of children's speech development. Educational activities organized by the teacher play a decisive role in forming and developing children's speech skills.

The teacher's professional knowledge, speech culture, and pedagogical mastery directly influence the level of children's speech development. The teacher's speech serves as the main model for children. Correct pronunciation, rich vocabulary, and grammatically accurate, fluent speech help form children's speech culture.

During communication, the teacher should use simple, clear, and expressive speech, encourage children to listen actively, and express their thoughts freely.

In addition, the teacher must identify speech errors in time and correct them politely and pedagogically. Eliminating deficiencies through encouragement and support rather than harsh criticism increases children's speech activity and strengthens their self-confidence.

The teacher's methodological preparation also plays an important role. Using various methods and techniques and considering children's age and individual characteristics ensures the effectiveness of speech development. When planning the educational process, the teacher should clearly define goals and tasks aimed at speech development.

CONCLUSION

The development of preschool children's speech is one of the important directions of the educational process. A child's speech development directly affects thinking, communication with the environment, and social adaptation. Research results show that taking age and individual characteristics into account and supporting children's speech activity are essential in the speech development process.

Using effective pedagogical approaches ensures the consistent formation of phonetic, lexical, and grammatical speech. The teacher's speech literacy, the quality of communication with children, and the proper organization of the educational environment positively influence speech development. It was also determined that forming independent thinking and the ability to express ideas freely is one of the main tasks of preschool education.

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